

Students' Perception of The Implementation of Running Dictation in Teaching Reading

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ABSTRACT: This study examines students' perceptions of using Running Dictation as a teaching strategy in reading applied by the teacher in the seventh grade of Junior High School in Bandar Lampung. A descriptive quantitative approach was employed, with data collected through a structured questionnaire. The sample included 20 students. The data collection technique involved distributing a closed-ended questionnaire to gather quantitative data on students' perceptions including awareness, past experiences, motivation, knowledge, and social interaction. The questionnaire consists of 10 positive and 10 negative statements to assess students' perception of the Running Dictation strategy. The responses were measured using a Likert scale, ranging from "Strongly Agree" to "Strongly Disagree." The results are categorized into two main types of perceptions: positive and negative. The results indicate that most students positively perceived running dictation in reading instruction. Specifically, 10 students agreed, 7 strongly agreed, and 3 were neutral in response to statements about these benefits. Conversely, the negative statements in the questionnaire, designed to assess any difficulties or drawbacks of Running Dictation, received limited agreement. Overall, the results suggest that most students found Running Dictation beneficial, noting increased engagement and comprehension through its active and collaborative approach to reading.

KEYWORDS: Comprehension, Perception, Running Dictation, Strategy, Teaching Reading.

INTRODUCTION

Learning English requires proficiency in four key areas: listening, writing, speaking, and reading. These skills are interrelated and often build upon each other. While all four skills are important, reading is frequently regarded as their most critical. Through reading, students gain access to new knowledge, process information, and expand their understanding of the world. According to Cooper et al. (1988), reading is not just a mechanical process of recognizing words but an active process that involves constructing or developing meaning from texts. In addition, Furthermore, Harmer (2003) adds another dimension to this understanding, stating that reading involves extracting meaning from the discourse presented in the text. Meanwhile, Grabe and Stoller (2011) further clarify the process of reading, defining it as a method of extracting information from a text and forming an interpretation of that information. This definition underlines that reading is not just about extracting surface-level information, but also about synthesizing new knowledge from the material encountered.

In the context of academic learning, reading comprehension becomes a vital skill, allowing students to extract meaning from texts and apply this knowledge to other learning areas. Reading comprehension is central to academic success, as it enables students to understand and interpret information from various sources. According to Rudell (2005), reading comprehension is one of the most important goals of academic reading. This is because comprehension enables students to use reading as a tool for both acquiring information and deriving pleasure from reading.

However, studies have shown that reading becomes the most challenging and frustrating skill for students to develop, as they may perceive it as a tedious task rather than an engaging activity (McKenna et al, 1995). The students do not know how to engage with the text actively, they are likely to experience comprehension breakdowns, particularly with longer or more challenging passages (Snow, 2002).

Moreover, the students become passive learners rather than active participants in their reading journey (Guthrie & Davis, 2003). They lack interactive experiences, then it causes them to miss out on opportunities to analyze and discuss texts, which are critical for

comprehension (Almasi & Garas-York, 2009; Guthrie, Wigfield, & Humenick, 2006). Some students struggle with comprehension and often avoid reading because it feels frustrating or overly challenging (Torgesen et al., 2007). Consequently, the students are less likely to enjoy reading because they do not fully understand the material. Some aspects are believed to have resulted in the classroom environment during reading sessions being dull and uninspiring, lacking a dynamic atmosphere that could otherwise motivate students to participate actively (Guthrie & Davis, 2003).

Furthermore, many classrooms rely heavily on a teacher-centered approach, which can overshadow opportunities for students to engage with texts in a meaningful way. This approach often involves direct instruction where students passively receive information, with limited involvement in discussing or questioning the content (Frey & Fisher, 2008; Guthrie, Wigfield, & Humenick, 2006). Such an environment reduces students' chances to actively participate and engage critically with the reading material. Without interactive reading activities, such as group discussions, peer reviews, or reading games, students may feel detached and view reading as an isolated, teacher-driven task rather than an interactive process (Guthrie, Wigfield, & Humenick, 2006). Moreover, according to Allington (2012), the teaching and learning process is often monotonous which leads to students feeling bored and disengaged. The limited exposure to diverse and engaging reading materials often results in disinterest.

Based on the researcher's preliminary research, found that many students have difficulty understanding and analyzing the content of what they read. This often stems from an overemphasis on memorization rather than comprehension strategies, resulting in a superficial understanding of texts. They also faced limited vocabulary knowledge is a primary barrier to comprehension. When students frequently encounter unfamiliar words, they struggle to understand the meaning of sentences and grasp the overall context, which can lead to frustration and disengagement. Reading can feel like a daunting task, especially if the material does not relate to students' interests or daily lives. Without motivation, students may read passively or avoid reading altogether, further hindering their language development. Many students struggle to remember details, main ideas, and key points after reading. This retention issue is often due to ineffective reading strategies and a lack of engagement with the material. Students also tend to translate texts word-for-word from English to their native language, rather than focusing on understanding the meaning directly in English. This habit can slow down the reading speed and impede comprehension.

One potential solution to that issue is the use of innovative and engaging teaching methods, such as the Running Dictation technique. Running Dictation is an interactive classroom activity where students work in pairs or small groups to read, memorize, and transcribe a passage placed at a distance. This activity combines reading, writing, movement, and teamwork, making it an effective way to engage students in reading while also addressing reading comprehension challenges. By incorporating kinesthetic, visual, and auditory learning styles, Running Dictation caters to diverse student needs and can increase engagement levels compared to traditional reading exercises.

Research by Gardner (1993) on multiple intelligences emphasizes the importance of addressing different learning modalities in the classroom to maximize student engagement and learning outcomes. Running Dictation is particularly effective because it engages students physically, encouraging them to move while simultaneously reinforcing their reading and comprehension skills.

In addition, Running Dictation encourages this collaboration as students must work together to complete the task, communicate their understanding, and help each other recall information. Unlike passive learning strategies, Running Dictation promotes active participation and engagement, allowing students to learn more dynamically and interactively. Bonwell and Eison (1991) assert that active learning, where students engage with the material and reflect on their learning process, is more effective than traditional passive forms of learning. According to Medina (2008), the use of interactive and physically engaging activities has been shown to improve student concentration, task persistence, and memory. Furthermore, Baddeley's (2000) model of working memory suggests that activities involving reading, memorization, and recall can enhance cognitive function by actively engaging both phonological and visuospatial memory. These cognitive processes are critical for improving students' ability to process and retain information, particularly when learning a second language.

However, the success of Running Dictation as an instructional tool is largely influenced by students' perceptions and attitudes, which play a critical role in determining how effectively they engage with and benefit from the activity. When students view an activity positively, they are more likely to participate actively, approach tasks with enthusiasm, and ultimately retain more of what they learn.

Conversely, if students find an activity challenging or unclear in purpose, their motivation and willingness to engage may diminish, potentially reducing the technique's impact on learning outcomes.

In addition, students' perceptions can shape various aspects of their learning experience, including their motivation to participate, level of engagement, sense of enjoyment, and perceived value of the activity. Running Dictation requires students to step out of traditional passive learning roles and take on more interactive, communicative ones. As a result, how students feel about these roles—whether they feel excited, competent, or even apprehensive—can influence the degree to which they benefit from this approach. Furthermore, their attitudes toward the collaborative and physical components of Running Dictation can impact the overall classroom atmosphere, either enhancing or limiting the sense of teamwork and motivation that supports language acquisition.

This study therefore aims to delve deeply into students' perceptions of the implementation of Running Dictation in reading instruction, examining both the benefits and challenges they encounter. By capturing students' perspectives, this research intends to shed light on how Running Dictation is received by learners and whether they find it helpful in strengthening reading comprehension, engagement, and language processing. Insights gained from these perceptions can guide the teacher in refining their use of Running Dictation, tailoring it to better meet students' needs, and overcoming any obstacles they might face in using this approach. Ultimately, this study seeks to contribute to a broader understanding of how these innovative, interactive techniques can be optimized for students to improve reading comprehension and overall language learning. Based on the background, the research question is as follows: What is the student's perception of the implementation of running dictation in teaching reading?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Reading Comprehension

Reading comprehension involves several essential components, including decoding, vocabulary knowledge, fluency, and the ability to make inferences. These components work together to ensure that the reader fully understands the text. In addition, reading comprehension also requires critical thinking, as readers must analyze, evaluate, and synthesize information from the text. Paul and Elder (2014) argue that critical readers not only understand what is written but also assess its validity and relevance.

Moreover, reading comprehension is influenced by a range of cognitive, emotional, and environmental factors. Cognitive factors such as memory, attention, and cognitive flexibility are integral to processing and understanding text. Emotional factors, such as motivation and interest, also play a crucial role. Students who find reading tasks engaging are more likely to comprehend and retain the information they read (Schunk & Zimmerman, 2007). Additionally, the reading environment, including teacher support and access to resources, can significantly impact comprehension outcomes.

Since reading comprehension is essential not only for academic achievement but also for everyday functioning. It allows individuals to follow instructions, access information, and make informed decisions. Students, those who struggle with reading comprehension often experience difficulties in other subjects because they cannot fully engage with written content, whether it's solving math word problems, interpreting science texts, or understanding historical documents (Snow, 2010).

In conclusion, reading comprehension is a multifaceted skill that involves various cognitive processes such as decoding, vocabulary knowledge, fluency, and critical thinking. It plays a vital role in academic success and lifelong learning. Educators play an essential role in fostering reading comprehension by using effective teaching strategies and creating a supportive learning environment. By addressing the components of reading comprehension, students can develop the skills necessary to become proficient and confident readers, equipped to tackle both academic and real-world challenges.

Concept of Running Dictation

Running Dictation is a dynamic and interactive strategy that integrates multiple language skills, including reading, writing, listening, and speaking. The concept of Running Dictation has been extensively bandied by various students, each emphasizing its unique benefits and operations in the language literacy process. According to Newton (2009), Running Dictation is a form of dictation where a short textbook is compartmented in a large fountain and posted on a wall outside the classroom. Students working in groups must read and study the textbook before decreeing it to their group members who write it down. The exertion encourages collaboration, physical movement, and commerce, offering a fun and engaging way for scholars to exercise their language chops.

In addition, Hess (2001) elaborates that Running Dictation is a group exertion where each group consists of two places the runner and the writer. The runner is responsible for going to the textbook, reading and learning the judgment, and also returning to the writer to mandate the judgment. The writer must also transcribe the judgment as directly as possible. This structure allows scholars to engage in collaborative literacy, with each member contributing to the success of the exertion. The cooperative nature of the exercise fosters communication, cooperation, and problem-solving aspects, all while buttressing language literacy.

In addition, Chai (2011) further reinforces the idea that Running Dictation is particularly salutary for students who enjoy working in groups and being physically active. The exertion not only promotes academic literacy but also caters to scholars' social and interactive requirements, as it allows them to work together in a probative, group-grounded terrain. This aspect makes Running Dictation a suitable exertion for different literacy styles, as it combines audible, visual, and kinesthetic rudiments. According to Alex (2013), Running Dictation is a fun task that incorporates reading, harkening, and jotting, which aligns with the conception of a holistic literacy experience. This approach fosters scholars' engagement with the language and improves their capability to concentrate on different language chops contemporaneously.

Furthermore, Gültekin (2014) emphasizes that dictation strategies like Running Dictation can help scholars identify and correct spelling crimes, as they bear active engagement with the textbook. In this process, scholars enhance their jotting capacities, particularly their spelling and grammatical delicacy. Dictation allows scholars to exercise their language chops in a controlled, yet interactive manner, leading to bettered jotting proficiency. This fashion is especially useful for buttressing vocabulary and alphabet operation in the environment, as scholars must recall and produce language they've just read.

The substance of Running Dictation falsehoods in its capability to combine colorful rudiments of language accession — reading, writing, listening, and speaking — into a single, cohesive exertion. The runner's task of reading and learning the textbook improves their reading appreciation and retention aspect. The pen's part of transcribing the textbook enhances their jotting capacities and helps solidify their understanding of correct judgment structure, spelling, and alphabet. also, the demand for communication between the runner and the pen promotes listening and speaking, making Running Dictation a comprehensive language learning tool.

The teacher's part in this exertion is vital. Depending on the requirements and proficiency situations of the scholars, the teacher can modify the procedure of Running Dictation to target specific chops or language areas. For illustration, if the focus is on perfecting vocabulary retention, the teacher may choose textbooks that introduce new words and expressions. Alternately, if the thing is to strengthen judgment structure and alphabet, the teacher may elect passages that punctuate particular grammatical structures. This rigidity makes handling Dictation an effective tool for addressing a wide range of learning objects.

In conclusion, Running Dictation is an interactive and multifaceted exertion that supports the development of essential language chops. By combining physical movement with cognitive engagement, not only enhances scholars' jotting and reading capacities but also promotes collaboration, communication, and critical thinking. The inflexibility of Running Dictation allows it to be acclimatized to meet the different requirements of scholars, making it a precious tutoring strategy in language education. Whether used to support vocabulary, alphabet, or overall language ignorance, Running Dictation proves to be a largely effective and pleasurable system for enhancing language accession.

Concept of Perception

Perception is deduced from the Latin word *percipio*, refers to the process of organizing, relating, and interpreting sensitive information to represent and understand the terrain. It involves how become apprehensive of, regard, or interpret the world around us through our senses similar as sight, hail, touch, taste, and smell. According to the Oxford Dictionary (2016), perception is the capability to see, hear, or become apprehensive of a commodity, and it goes beyond bare sensitive events to include how a commodity is understood or interpreted by an existent. Perception enables us to make sense of the world and guide our conduct and responses grounded on that understanding.

Barry (1998) explains that perception is the process through which fete, organize, and make sense of stimulants in our terrain propositions of perception generally vary in terms of the emphasis placed on the places of sensation and advanced cognitive processes. Some propositions suggest that perception begins with introductory sensitive input, while others punctuate the significance of cognitive factors similar as memory, attention, and previous knowledge in shaping how we perceive the world. This distinction

underscores that perception isn't simply an unresistant event of external stimulants but involves complex cognitive processing that allows us to interpret and respond to the world meaningfully.

Ponty (1945) takes this further by suggesting that perception is unnaturally tied to our physical actuality. He argues that mortal experience isn't simply a matter of intellectual understanding or detached observation, but is deeply embedded in our embodied engagement with the world. In his view, perception is an active, complementary relationship between the perceiver and the terrain. Rather than seeing perception as an unresistant event of sensitive data — an idea current in the Cartesian gospel — Merleau-Ponty emphasizes that we laboriously engage with our surroundings, interpreting and responding to them as we navigate the world. This perspective asserts that perception isn't just an internal or cognitive process but is thick from our physical body, which shapes how we witness and understand the world around us.

In this sense, perception can be seen as an ongoing, dynamic process. It isn't simply a detached intellectual exertion but an embodied, lived experience where we continuously engage with and make sense of our surroundings. This engagement isn't just about taking in sensitive data but also about interpreting, replying to, and acting on that data. In short, perception is the process through which we elect, admit, organize, and interpret information from our terrain in a way that makes it meaningful and useful for us. It allows us to navigate the world, make opinions, and interact with the terrain coherently and effectively.

Therefore, perception is both a cognitive and sensitive process — an active interpretation of the world that draws upon not only the immediate sensitive input but also previous guests, feelings, and contextual knowledge. It allows individuals to make sense of their surroundings, fete patterns, and respond meetly to the stimulants they encounter. Perception is essential in helping us navigate our everyday lives, from introductory tasks to more complex decision-timber, by enabling us to interpret the world and engage with it meaningfully.

In conclusion, perception highlights it as an embodied, dynamic process that transcends bare cognitive or sensitive input. Perception, in this view, is an active and complementary relationship between the perceiver and the terrain, embedded in our physical presence in the world. Rather than passively entering sensitive data, also interpret and respond to our surroundings, drawing on once gestures, feelings, and contextual understanding to produce meaning. This approach underscores perception as an aspect of mortal experience, essential for navigating, interpreting, and interacting with the world in a coherent, purposeful way.

RESEARCH METHOD

In this research, the researcher employed a descriptive quantitative method, which aims to describe the characteristics of a phenomenon or a population through the collection and analysis of numerical data. Descriptive quantitative research is useful in capturing patterns, trends, and relationships between variables clearly and objectively. This method is commonly used when the goal is to assess the current state of a particular issue without manipulating the variables under study. In this case, the researcher aimed to explore and understand the perceptions of students regarding the use of Running Dictation as a teaching technique for reading.

The researcher acted as a nonparticipant, meaning that they did not actively engage in the classroom activities or interfere with the normal course of events. Instead, the researcher focused solely on collecting data using a questionnaire as the primary research instrument. The nonparticipant role is essential in maintaining objectivity and ensuring that the data collection process does not influence the students' responses or behaviors.

The population for this research consisted of seventh-grade students at Permata Bunda Junior High School for the academic year 2024-2025. The total population in this study was comprised of a single class, which included 20 students. Hatch and Farhady (1982) describe a sample as a subset of a population that is selected for a study. To ensure that the sample accurately reflects the larger population, the sample must be representative. For this study, the sample was selected using a purposive sampling technique. Purposive sampling involves selecting participants who meet specific criteria relevant to the research study. In this case, the researcher chose the class that was already familiar with and had used Running Dictation, making it a suitable group to assess their perceptions of the technique.

This research involved two key variables: the independent variable and the dependent variable. The independent variable refers to the factor that is being manipulated or assessed for its effect on another variable, while the dependent variable is the outcome that is being

measured. In this study, the independent variable is the students' perceptions of teaching reading, while the dependent variable is the use of Running Dictation. By focusing on these variables, the researcher sought to understand what students perceive the effectiveness of Running Dictation as a teaching method for reading comprehension.

The primary instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire, designed to capture the students' positive and negative perceptions of the use of Running Dictation in teaching reading. The questionnaire consisted of 20 statements, to which the students were asked to respond based on their feelings and experiences with the technique. The questionnaire allowed the researcher to quantify the students' perceptions and categorize their responses as either positive or negative.

Before the students completed the questionnaire, the researcher provided clear instructions on how to answer the questions and ensured that the students understood the purpose of the survey. The students were given 15 minutes to fill out the questionnaire. This time frame was sufficient to allow the students to carefully consider and respond to each statement. Once the questionnaires were collected, the researcher began the process of classifying and analyzing the data. The responses were categorized into positive and negative perceptions based on the student's answers.

The type of data collected in this research was primarily quantitative, derived from the student's responses to the questionnaire. By analyzing this data, the researcher aimed to gain insights into the students' perceptions of the use of Running Dictation as a method for teaching reading. The findings from this analysis provided valuable information that could inform future teaching practices and contribute to a better understanding of the effectiveness of interactive techniques like Running Dictation in the classroom. Through this process, the researcher was able to conclude the students' attitudes toward the technique and its potential benefits or limitations.

RESULT

Analysis of the salient points of the data resulted in a total of 5 categories of students' perceptions. These categories will be used to answer the research question: What is the student's perception of the implementation of running dictation in teaching reading?

The result of this study reveals that students' perceptions of using Running Dictation in teaching reading can be categorized into two main types: positive and negative perceptions, with the majority of responses leaning towards the positive side. Many students expressed high levels of motivation and awareness as a result of participating in the Running Dictation activity. The dynamic and interactive nature of the task helped to capture their attention and sustain their focus, making the learning process more engaging and enjoyable. For students, the physical aspect of moving around and the excitement of collaborating with peers created a sense of energy and interest in the reading task. This heightened motivation allowed them to stay focused on reading and language tasks in a more meaningful way, which directly contributed to their improved engagement with the content.

Moreover, the activity encouraged students to develop a greater awareness of language form, particularly at the phrase and clause levels. As they transcribed what they heard, students became more mindful of sentence structure, grammar, and language usage, which deepened their understanding of how language works. This awareness not only helped them improve their reading and writing skills but also expanded their overall linguistic competence. The activity's structure, which involved immediate feedback on students' performance, also facilitated self-awareness. Students could identify their mistakes in real time, and this allowed them to make corrections and refine their understanding of language, fostering a sense of achievement and progress in their learning.

Meanwhile, social interaction played a significant role in the Running Dictation process, as students were required to work collaboratively. The cooperative nature of the activity allowed students to interact with their peers, share ideas, and help one another in completing the task. Many students highlighted that they felt more connected to their classmates during this process. The social aspect not only enhanced their ability to communicate and work as a team but also created a supportive learning environment. Through helping each other solve problems and discuss content, students developed stronger social bonds, which, in turn, encouraged their active participation and learning.

In addition to social interaction, Running Dictation also provided students with the opportunity to increase their knowledge, particularly in terms of vocabulary and language structure. As they repeated and transcribed phrases, students expanded their vocabulary, learned new words, and became more familiar with common sentence structures. The activity encouraged them to think critically about language and comprehension, which led to an increase in their knowledge of both the reading material and the language

itself. Students’ past experiences with learning also influenced their perceptions. For many, the activity served as a refreshing break from traditional learning methods, offering a hands-on, interactive approach that helped them connect with the material in a new way. For those with previous exposure to similar cooperative learning techniques, Running Dictation seemed like a familiar and enjoyable challenge, reinforcing their positive attitudes toward language learning.

However, despite the overwhelmingly positive perceptions, some students expressed negative views, particularly regarding the physical demands and time constraints of the activity. The running aspect, while beneficial for keeping the students active, was seen as tiring by some, and it distracted them from focusing entirely on the reading material. Additionally, the time pressure sometimes caused stress, especially for students who found it difficult to keep pace with the activity’s speed. This pressure may have affected their ability to process and comprehend the text fully, leading to frustration for some learners.

Based on the result, student’s perception of the use of Running Dictation can be categorized into the following figure.

Figure 4.1 Category of the Student’s Perception of the Implementation of Running Dictation.

The figure above shows that the positive perception for all indicators was higher, meanwhile, the negative perception for all indicators was the lowest one. It means that the students gave a positive perception of being taught by running dictation technique, especially for social interaction.

To get the main score of the students, the writer used the following formula.

$$x = \frac{\sum x}{N}$$

$$x = \frac{176}{233}$$

$$x = 76\%$$

The majority of respondents have a positive perception across all indicators, with social interaction showing the strongest results (76% positive). However, areas such as experience, motivation, and knowledge still have room for improvement, as around 30% of respondents fall into the negative category for these indicators.

Moreover, 71% of the respondents reported positive past experiences, while 29% indicated negative experiences. This suggests that the majority have had favorable encounters, but a significant minority might have faced challenges that impacted their perception.

In addition, 75% of the participants have a positive level of awareness, it is evident that most individuals are well-informed and conscious of the subject at hand. However, 25% remain in the negative category, indicating some gaps in awareness.

Furthermore, 70% of the respondents displayed positive motivation. This indicates a strong drive and willingness to engage, though 30% of respondents showed lower motivation, which could affect overall engagement or participation.

Similar to motivation, 70% have a positive knowledge level. This means that most respondents possess the necessary understanding, though a portion (30%) lacks sufficient knowledge, possibly creating a barrier to more effective involvement.

To find out how students' perceptions of the Running Dictation strategy, students are asked to respond by completing the questionnaire and answering 20 questions in the form of a complete answer. The answers are summarized in Table 4.1, whereas written responses are described separately.

Table 4.1 The Questionnaire of Students' Perception of Learning Scale

1	2	3	4	5
Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree

No.	Questions	1	2	3	4	5
Awareness						
1	I feel that this learning makes reading narrative texts easier and more enjoyable	0%	0%	0%	45%	55%
2	I feel that this learning didn't give me a deep understanding	45%	55%	0%	0%	0%
3	I feel that this activity makes me easier to comprehend reading text	0%	0%	10%	50%	40%
4	I didn't get many advantages after the learning process	60%	40%	0%	0%	0%
Past experience						
5	I feel that this learning offers a lot of experience for students	0%	0%	15%	60%	25%
6	I did not find it easy to understand the lesson when the teacher taught me	40%	40%	20%	0%	0%
7	I learned to read narrative texts well in groups during the learning	0%	0%	10%	60%	30%
8	I can't practice critical thinking in this reading activity	40%	60%	0%	0%	0%
Knowledge						
9	I gained much knowledge about narrative reading after this learning	0%	0%	25%	45%	30%
10	This learning activity did not increase my understanding of reading text	45%	50%	5%	0%	0%
11	I have a lot of progress in comprehending reading text through this learning	0%	0%	40%	50%	10%
12	I found difficulties understanding reading text during this learning	40%	45%	15%	0%	0%
Motivation						
13	This learning motivates me to work together in groups	0%	0%	20%	65%	15%
14	I feel that this learning hasn't influenced my interest in reading	40%	45%	15%	0%	0%

15	This Learning can increase my motivation to read more comprehensively	0%	0%	0%	75%	25%
16	This learning makes me unmotivated to read English text	45%	40%	15%	0%	0%
Social Interaction						
17	This kind of learning is very suitable for group investigation	0%	0%	5%	55%	40%
18	This learning did not increase cooperation in groups	60%	40%	0%	0%	0%
19	In my opinion, students will help each other if the teacher uses this attractive and innovative strategy	0%	0%	0%	55%	45%
20	This kind of learning can make me interact with other friends	55%	45%	0%	0%	0%

DISCUSSIONS

Thus, the highest positive response, 76%, was observed in social interaction. This shows that most individuals feel comfortable and engaged in interactions with others. Only 24% of the findings from this study reveal valuable insights into the students' perceptions of the Running Dictation activity used in teaching reading. Overall, the majority of respondents demonstrated positive perceptions across various indicators, particularly social interaction, which stood out as the most favorable aspect of the activity. However, certain areas, such as motivation, experience, knowledge, and awareness, revealed room for improvement. These results provide a nuanced understanding of how Running Dictation can affect students' engagement and learning outcomes, and they suggest areas where the teaching strategy could be further refined.

Social Interaction as a Key Strength

The highest positive response observed was in the area of social interaction, with 76% of respondents reporting positive experiences. This aligns with research by Johnson and Johnson (1989), who argue that cooperative learning, where social interaction plays a central role, leads to higher levels of engagement, academic achievement, and interpersonal skills. The Running Dictation activity, which encourages collaboration between students, helps create a more interactive and supportive learning environment. As students work together to transcribe phrases and phrases, they engage in problem-solving and idea exchange, which fosters a sense of community. These findings support previous studies that emphasize the importance of social interaction in the learning process, highlighting that cooperative activities can enhance students' social skills and motivation to learn (Slavin, 1995). Given the high levels of positive social interaction, Running Dictation appears to be particularly effective in fostering a collaborative and communicative classroom atmosphere.

Motivation, Knowledge, and Awareness: Areas for Improvement

While 70% of the respondents reported positive motivation levels, a significant 30% expressed lower motivation, which may affect overall engagement. Motivation is a critical factor in learning, as it directly influences students' willingness to participate and their persistence in overcoming challenges (Ryan & Deci, 2000). In the context of Running Dictation, the activity's physical and interactive nature is generally seen as motivating, yet some students may find it difficult to stay engaged due to various personal or contextual factors, such as learning styles or previous experiences with the activity. A more differentiated approach, where the activity is tailored to different student needs, might be beneficial in increasing motivation levels across the board.

Similarly, while 70% of students reported having positive knowledge levels, 30% lacked sufficient knowledge, which could hinder their participation. Research has shown that a strong foundation of prior knowledge plays a significant role in students' ability to understand and engage with new learning content (Sweller, 1988). In the case of Running Dictation, students with less knowledge may struggle to accurately transcribe or understand the language being used, which can affect their ability to fully benefit from the activity. Addressing these knowledge gaps through preparatory exercises or scaffolding may help ensure that all students are equipped with the necessary background knowledge to engage effectively.

Awareness, while generally positive (75% of respondents), also showed room for improvement, as 25% of students reported lower levels of awareness. Awareness in the learning process is linked to metacognitive skills, such as the ability to monitor one's understanding and adjust strategies accordingly (Flavell, 1979). Students who are aware of their learning processes tend to perform better because they can recognize areas where they need improvement and seek strategies to address these gaps. The 25% of students with negative awareness may benefit from activities or instruction that enhance their metacognitive skills, helping them become more reflective and proactive in their learning.

Experience: A Mixed Response

In terms of experience, 71% of respondents reported positive past experiences with the activity, suggesting that Running Dictation was perceived as a valuable learning strategy. However, 29% indicated negative experiences, which raises questions about the challenges some students faced. Past experiences can significantly influence how students approach new learning activities (Zimmerman, 2002). Negative experiences, such as difficulties in understanding the activity or physical discomfort, could affect students' perceptions and participation in future activities. Identifying the sources of these negative experiences and addressing them—perhaps through clearer instructions or adjustments to the pacing of the activity—could help improve student engagement and satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

Eventually, the result suggests that Running Dictation is an effective strategy for encouraging social commerce and promoting engagement in teaching reading. Moreover, to further enhance its effectiveness, attention should be given to areas analogous to motivation, knowledge, and awareness, where there's still room for improvement. Accommodating the exertion to meet the different conditions of students, offering scaffolding to fill knowledge gaps, and fostering metacognitive awareness could lead to indeed lower success in students' issues. Ultimately, by addressing these challenges, teachers can maximize the eventuality of Running Dictation as a strategy for reading, creating a more inclusive and effective knowledge terrain.

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